

Figure S2. Posterior probability for each amino acid of the 12 reconstructed ancestral sequences shown in **Fig. S1**. The most probable sequence for nodes CaPo (**A**), CaCD (**B**), AVP (**C**) and ALiP (**D**), and two alternative sequences (bis and tris) for each of them (see Methods for sampling strategy) are included. The probabilities of Trp172 in AVP and ALiP sequences are 0.999 and 1.000, respectively; and that of Asn183 in ALiP sequences is 0.993. The mean probabilities for every reconstructed sequence are also shown.

Figure S3. Proximal histidine, neighbor residues and distances (Å) in ancestral peroxidases (His177) and extant CcP (2CYP; His175) and *P. chrysosporium* LiPH8 (1B82; His176). His177-Asp239 and Ser/Thr178-Asp202 H-bonds would affect the position of the proximal histidine in the ancestral peroxidases, and consequently the heme iron electron-deficiency (homologous H-bonds are present in LiPH8, but the second one is absent from CcP). Distal histidine (His48 in the ancestors, His52 in CcP, and His47 in LiPH8) is also shown.

Figure S4. Surface environment of catalytic tryptophan. Electrostatic surfaces computed for ancestral CaCD (**A**), AVP (**B**) and ALiP (**C**) homology models, and extant LiPH8 (**D**) crystal structure (PDB 1B82) showing the environment of the exposed tryptophan (magenta spheres, yellow labels) in **B-D**, and the equivalent alanine residue in **A** (the positions of neighbor residues are also indicated). The presence of the catalytic tryptophan in AVP and ALiP and the absence of a net negative environment, as found in LiPH8 that is unable to oxidize RB5, contribute to the oxidation of this anionic dye by the two ancestral enzymes. The opposite effect is expected for VA, whose cation radical would be stabilized by the negative environment in LiPH8.